

Advanced Modular Machine Tools: A Comprehensive Approach to High-Performance Boring Machine Design

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Abstract: The design and development of modular machine tools necessitate a precise approach to ensure efficiency, accuracy, and adaptability in modern manufacturing environments. This paper outlines a comprehensive methodology for designing a boring machine, focusing on the modular machine tool's main components and transmission systems. The study begins by highlighting the characteristics and proposal stages of modular machine tools, emphasizing the importance of standardization and adaptability. The technical design phase involves detailed finite element analysis (FEA) and material selection to optimize mechanical properties and ensure robustness. The multi-axle box, a crucial component, is designed to drive multiple spindles efficiently. Various transmission schemes were evaluated, with Scheme 3 emerging as the most feasible due to its balance of structural layout and cost-effectiveness, despite the increased load on the active spindle. Power calculations ensure the machine's capability to handle required machining operations without overloading. The spindle design, gear parameters, and shaft dimensions are meticulously calculated and verified for strength and durability. Integration of advanced automation and control systems, along with economic analysis, further enhances the machine tool's efficiency and viability. The design principles and calculations presented in this paper provide a robust framework for developing high-performance modular machine tools, capable of meeting diverse manufacturing requirements with precision and reliability.

Keywords: Modular Machine Tools, Boring Machine Design, Multi-Axle Box, Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Transmission System Optimization.

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Introduction

Modular machine tools represent a significant advancement in modern manufacturing, providing flexibility and efficiency by integrating standardized components with specialized elements to perform multiple machining operations simultaneously. These tools are designed to adapt quickly to changing production requirements, offering a critical

advantage in dynamic manufacturing environments. The ability to reconfigure modular machine tools for different tasks with minimal downtime and cost has made them indispensable in achieving high efficiency and quality in production processes [1]. The design of modular machine tools involves a meticulous approach, beginning with the proposal stage where the process plan is developed. This stage is crucial as it determines whether the machine tool can meet the stringent requirements of being compact, lightweight, simple in structure, highly efficient, and capable of producing high-quality outputs [2]. During this phase, the structural characteristics, dimensional accuracy, surface roughness, and technical requirements of the workpieces are analyzed in detail. This includes understanding the positioning and clamping methods, as well as the tools and auxiliary equipment required for processing [3]. Technical design follows, involving the creation of detailed diagrams and specifications for each component of the machine tool. This includes the multi-axle box, which is pivotal for housing and driving multiple spindles based on the machining schematic diagram [4]. The use of Finite Element Analysis (FEA) to simulate mechanical behavior under operational loads ensures the robustness and reliability of the design [5]. The integration of hydraulic, pneumatic, and electronic controls further enhances the precision and functionality of the machine tool, enabling seamless automation and real-time adjustments to maintain optimal performance [6]. One of the primary challenges in the design of modular machine tools is ensuring the accuracy and stability of the machine tool assembly. The machine tool connection dimension chain diagram is essential in this regard, depicting the spatial relationships and connections between various components. This diagram ensures that all parts fit together correctly and function as intended, maintaining high precision in the final assembly [7]. Additionally, the selection of appropriate materials, such as high-quality carbon steel for shafts, and the implementation of heat treatment processes to improve wear resistance and fatigue strength, are critical to the machine's performance [8]. The multi-axle box transmission design is another focal point of this research. Various transmission schemes were evaluated to ensure the effective distribution of power and motion to each spindle. Through detailed analysis and comparison, a transmission design was selected that balances structural layout and cost-effectiveness while maintaining the necessary torque and speed for machining operations [9]. The integration of automation and control systems, including advanced algorithms and human-machine interfaces, further optimizes the cutting process and ensures consistent quality [10].

Methodology

1. Overall Design Plan of Modular Machine Tool

1.1 Steps for Designing Modular Machine Tools

1.1.1 Characteristics of Modular Machine Tools

Modular machine tools are based on general components and equipped with specialized components to process one or several workpieces according to predetermined processes. They can perform simultaneous machining of workpieces with multiple cutters and holes, completing a series of cutting processes on an automatic production line. The general components used by modular machine tools and their automatic production lines are designed and manufactured according to the principles of standardization, serialization, and generalization. The modular design approach allows for flexibility and adaptability, enabling the machine tool to be reconfigured for different tasks with minimal downtime and cost. This adaptability is crucial in modern manufacturing environments where production requirements can change rapidly [14].

1.1.2 Proposal Stage

Developing a process plan is critical in designing modular machine tools. This step determines whether the machine tool can meet the requirements of "small size, light weight, simple structure, high efficiency, and good quality." It involves analyzing the drawings of the processed parts, understanding their structural characteristics, dimensional accuracy, surface roughness, technical requirements, positioning and clamping methods, process methods, tools, and auxiliary tools used in the processing process. The proposal stage also includes a feasibility study to evaluate the

economic and technical viability of the proposed design, considering factors such as material availability, manufacturing costs, and potential market demand [15].

1.1.3 Technical Design Stage

This stage requires drawing the multi-axle box equipment diagram. Based on the determined process and structural scheme, the design includes the distribution form of the main shaft and transmission shaft, and the selection of general components. Assembly drawings of the multi-axle box and other components are created. Detailed technical specifications for each component are developed, including material selection, dimensional tolerances, and surface finish requirements. Finite element analysis (FEA) is performed to simulate the mechanical behavior of the components under operational loads, ensuring the design's robustness and reliability. The technical design stage also involves creating detailed schematics for the control systems, including hydraulic, pneumatic, and electronic controls, which are integral to the machine's operation [16].

1.2 Formulation of Combined Machine Tool Scheme

1.2.1 Main Factors Affecting the Formulation of Modular Machine Tool Plans

The main factors include the machining accuracy and process of the processed parts, the machining process that needs to be completed on the combined machine tool, and the guaranteed machining accuracy. The spindle structure type and data parameters must be selected based on the material processing location and accuracy requirements, ensuring sufficient rigidity and vibration resistance. Additionally, thermal effects and their impact on machining accuracy are considered, with thermal analysis conducted to predict temperature distributions and their influence on the structural components. This ensures that the machine tool maintains high precision under varying operational conditions [18].

1.2.2 Issues to be Considered When Formulating Process Plans

Consider the precision and surface roughness achievable by common process methods, principles and precautions for determining the process plan, hole center distance, and positioning reference and clamping point selection. The arrangement of rough and precision machining processes must be reasonably solved according to the principle of economically meeting machining requirements. The process plan must also account for tool wear and maintenance schedules to ensure consistent performance. Advanced process simulation software is used to optimize the sequence of operations and predict potential issues, allowing for adjustments to be made before physical implementation [17].

1.2.3 Considerations for Determining the Configuration Type and Structural Scheme of Machine Tools

When determining the configuration type and structural scheme of the machine tool, consider the characteristics and applicability of modular machine tools, machining accuracy, the impact of different configuration types on accuracy, and process concentration issues. Configuring multiple axle boxes to process multiple holes on a power component to concentrate the process is a basic processing method for modular machine tools. The configuration must also consider ergonomic factors, ensuring that the machine tool is easy to operate and maintain. Additionally, the structural design should facilitate efficient chip removal and cooling to prevent overheating and ensure a clean working environment [19].

1.3 Determination of Cutting Amount and Selection of Cutting Tools

1.3.1 Selection of Cutting Parameters

The selection of cutting parameters involves determining the cutting speed v , feed rate f , and depth of cut a based on the material and processing requirements of the workpiece. The parameters are optimized to achieve the desired machining accuracy and surface finish while maintaining tool life. The cutting speed v is calculated using the formula:

$$v = \pi \times D \times n$$

where D is the diameter of the cutting tool and n is the spindle speed. The selection process also considers the dynamic behavior of the machine tool, including vibrations and stability, to ensure that optimal cutting conditions are

maintained throughout the machining cycle.

1.3.2 Selection of Cutting Tools and Related Calculations

Cutting tools are selected based on the material characteristics of the workpiece and the required machining operations. The calculations involve determining the tool geometry, material, and coating to ensure efficient and accurate machining. Standard or simple cutting tools are chosen whenever possible to ensure reliability and ease of grinding. The selection process also includes evaluating tool holder designs and their impact on tool rigidity and vibration damping. The use of advanced materials, such as coated carbides and ceramics, is explored to enhance cutting performance and extend tool life. Detailed calculations are performed to determine the optimal tool paths and cutting forces, ensuring that the tools operate within their performance limits. The cutting force F_c can be estimated using:

$$F_c = k_c \times A$$

Where, k_c is the specific cutting force and A is the cross-sectional area of the cut.

1.3.3 Determination of Working Cycle and Stroke of Power Components

The working cycle of power components involves the process of moving from the original position to the final position and returning. It includes determining the work feed length (L_{work}), rapid introduction length (L_{rapid}), fast return length (L_{return}), and total travel of power components. The calculations ensure that the power components operate efficiently and accurately within the required stroke limits. The working cycle is optimized to minimize non-cutting time, enhancing overall productivity. Advanced motion control algorithms are used to synchronize the movements of the power components, ensuring smooth and precise operations. The design also incorporates feedback systems to monitor and adjust the working cycle in real-time, maintaining optimal performance under varying load conditions. The total stroke (L_{total}) can be calculated as:

$$L_{\text{total}} = L_{\text{work}} + L_{\text{rapid}} + L_{\text{return}}$$

2. Design and Calculation

The design and calculation phase involves creating detailed diagrams and performing calculations to ensure the modular machine tool meets all technical and operational requirements. This includes the process diagram for machining parts, schematic diagram of processed parts, and machine tool connection dimension chain diagram. Productivity calculations and design of main parts such as the spindle and gears are also carried out to ensure the machine tool's efficiency and reliability [20].

2.1 Process Diagram for Machining Parts

The process diagram outlines the sequence of operations required to machine the parts, detailing the specific machining steps, tools used, and required tolerances. This diagram serves as a blueprint for the entire machining process, ensuring that each step is executed with precision. The process diagram also includes annotations on material handling and inspection points, ensuring that quality control is maintained throughout the production cycle. The critical path method (CPM) is employed to identify the sequence of dependent tasks and optimize the production schedule, ensuring timely completion of each step [21].

2.2 Schematic Diagram of Processed Parts

The schematic diagram provides a detailed visual representation of the processed parts, illustrating the critical dimensions and features. This diagram is essential for verifying that the design meets all specifications and for identifying potential issues before fabrication. It also serves as a reference for assembly and quality control, ensuring that each part conforms to the design requirements. Geometric dimensioning and tolerancing (GD&T) principles are applied to specify the permissible variations in the geometry, ensuring interchangeability and proper fit during assembly.

2.3 Machine Tool Connection Dimension Chain Diagram

The machine tool connection dimension chain diagram depicts the spatial relationships and connections between the various components of the machine tool. This diagram ensures that all components fit together correctly and function as intended. It includes detailed measurements and alignment specifications, which are critical for maintaining the overall accuracy and stability of the machine tool. The dimensional chain can be analyzed using tolerance stack-up analysis to ensure that the accumulated tolerances do not exceed acceptable limits, maintaining high precision in the final assembly.

2.4 Productivity Calculations

Productivity calculations involve determining the machine tool's output based on the working cycle and cutting parameters. These calculations are essential for evaluating the efficiency and economic viability of the design. Factors such as tool change times, maintenance intervals, and operational downtime provide a realistic estimate of the machine tool's productivity. Simulation tools are used to model the production process and identify bottlenecks, allowing for optimization and improvements. The productivity P can be calculated using:

$$P = 60/T_{\text{cycle}}$$

where T_{cycle} is the total cycle time in minutes. Monte Carlo simulations are employed to model the variability in production parameters, providing a probabilistic assessment of the productivity under different scenarios.

2.5 Design of Main Parts

The design of main parts such as the spindle, gears, and tool holders involves detailed engineering analysis to ensure that each component meets the required performance standards. Finite element analysis (FEA) is used to simulate the mechanical stresses and deformations under operational loads, ensuring that the components are robust and reliable. Material selection and heat treatment processes are optimized to enhance the durability and performance of the components.

Detailed technical drawings and specifications are created for manufacturing, ensuring that each part is produced to the highest quality standards. The natural frequency (f_n) of the components is analyzed using:

$$f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$$

where k is the stiffness and m is the mass, to ensure that resonant frequencies are avoided during operation. Additionally, the stress-strain behavior of the components is examined using von Mises criteria to ensure that the materials can withstand the applied loads without yielding. The stress σ can be calculated using:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$$

where F is the applied force and A is the cross-sectional area. The von Mises stress is then used to compare with the material yield strength to ensure safety under loading conditions.

2.6 Integration of Automation and Control Systems

The integration of automation and control systems is a crucial aspect of the design, aimed at enhancing the machine tool's efficiency and precision. Advanced control algorithms are implemented to synchronize the movements of the power components, optimize the cutting process, and ensure consistent quality. The design includes the development of human-machine interfaces (HMIs) for easy operation and monitoring. Real-time data acquisition and feedback systems are integrated to continuously monitor the machine tool's performance, allowing for immediate adjustments and predictive maintenance. Control systems are designed using proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers, and their parameters are fine-tuned using techniques such as Ziegler-Nichols or Cohen-Coon methods to achieve optimal response times and stability. The integration also includes the use of Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) for sequence control and coordination of various subsystems.

The control system dynamics are modeled using differential equations, and the system response is analyzed using Laplace transforms. For instance, the transfer function $G(s)$ of a PID controller can be expressed as:

$$G(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s$$

where K_p, K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains, respectively. The system's stability and performance are evaluated using techniques such as root locus plots and Bode plots.

2.7 Economic Analysis

An economic analysis is conducted to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of the modular machine tool design. This analysis includes an assessment of initial investment costs, operational costs, maintenance expenses, and potential return on investment (ROI). Cost-saving measures, such as the use of standard components and efficient material utilization, are identified and implemented. The economic analysis also considers market demand and potential sales, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the design's financial viability. The net present value (NPV) and internal rate of return (IRR) are calculated to assess the profitability of the investment, using formulas:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^n \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

where C_t is the net cash inflow during the period t , r is the discount rate, and n is the number of periods.

IRR = r where NPV = 0

The payback period (PP) and benefit-cost ratio (BCR) are also calculated to provide additional insights into the economic feasibility:

$$PP = \frac{\text{Initial Investment}}{\text{Annual Cash Inflows}}$$

$$BCR = \frac{\text{Present Value of Benefits}}{\text{Present Value of Costs}}$$

2.8. Design of Main Parts

The design of main parts such as the spindle, gears, and tool holders involves detailed engineering analysis to ensure that each component meets the required performance standards. Finite element analysis (FEA) is used to simulate the mechanical stresses and deformations under operational loads, ensuring that the components are robust and reliable. Material selection and heat treatment processes are optimized to enhance the durability and performance of the components. Detailed technical drawings and specifications are created for manufacturing, ensuring that each part is produced to the highest quality standards. The natural frequency (f_n) of the components is analyzed using:

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$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$$

where F is the applied force and A is the cross-sectional area. The von Mises stress is then used to compare with the material yield strength to ensure safety under loading conditions. Additionally, fatigue analysis is conducted using the

S-N curve to predict the lifespan of the components under cyclic loading conditions, with the mean stress σ_m and alternating stress σ_a calculated as:

$$\sigma_m = \frac{\sigma_{\max} + \sigma_{\min}}{2}$$

$$\sigma_a = \frac{\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}}{2}$$

2.9. Integration of Automation and Control Systems

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$$G(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains, respectively. The system's stability and performance are evaluated using techniques such as root locus plots and Bode plots. Stability margins, gain margins, and phase margins are calculated to ensure robust performance under varying operational conditions.

3. Multi Axle Box - Right Main Axle Box Design

3.1 Design Steps for the Right Main Axle Box

3.1.1 Purpose and Classification of the Main Axle Box of Modular Machine Tools

The main axle box, particularly the right main axle box in modular machine tools, is a critical component designed to house multiple spindles. Its primary function is to arrange the spindles in accordance with the processing requirements and transmit power and motion from the motor or power components to each working spindle to achieve the required speeds and directions. The axle box ensures precise positioning and synchronization of the spindles, which is essential for the accuracy and efficiency of the machining process.

Main axle boxes can be classified into two categories based on their structural size:

Large Spindle Boxes: These are used for heavy-duty applications and are further divided into universal spindle boxes and specialized spindle boxes. The design of these boxes is complex, incorporating multiple specialized parts to handle larger workpieces and more demanding machining tasks.

Small Spindle Boxes: These are suitable for less demanding applications, involving fewer spindles and smaller workpieces.

3.1.2 Design Steps for the Right Main Axle Box

Designing the right main axle box involves several critical steps to ensure it meets the operational and structural requirements of the modular machine tool:

Initial Analysis: Conduct a thorough analysis of the processing requirements and the specifications of the workpieces. This includes determining the number of spindles, their positions, and the types of machining operations to be performed.

Dimensional Planning: Develop a detailed plan for the dimensions of the axle box, including the spacing between spindles, the overall size of the box, and the placement of support structures.

Material Selection: Select appropriate materials for the axle box and its components. Common materials include cast iron (e.g., HT200 for the box and HT150 for covers) due to their strength and vibration damping properties.

Finite Element Analysis (FEA): Perform FEA to simulate the mechanical behavior of the axle box under operational loads. This step helps identify potential stress points and areas where material reinforcement may be necessary.

Detailed Design and Modeling: Use CAD software to create detailed models of the axle box, incorporating all design specifications, including spindle placements, bearing housings, and cooling channels.

Prototyping and Testing: Develop a prototype of the axle box and conduct rigorous testing to validate its performance. Tests should include static and dynamic load tests, vibration analysis, and thermal performance tests.

Final Adjustments: Make necessary adjustments to the design based on testing results to ensure optimal performance and reliability.

3.2 Power Calculation of the Right Main Axle Box

The power calculation for the right main axle box is a crucial step to ensure that the machine can handle the required machining operations without overloading. This involves several calculations:

Cutting Power:

The cutting power (P_c) Required for each spindle can be calculated using the formula:

$$P_c = \frac{F_c \times v_c}{60 \times 1000}$$

where F_c is the cutting force in Newtons (N) and v_c is the cutting speed in meters per minute (m/min).

2. Total Cutting Power:

Sum the cutting power of all spindles to determine the total cutting power required (P_{total}) :

$$P_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{c_i}$$

where n is the number of spindles.

3. Idle Power:

Calculate the idle power (P_{idle}) required to overcome the mechanical resistance and friction of the moving parts when the machine is running without load.

4. Power Losses:

Estimate the power losses due to mechanical inefficiencies (P_{loss}), typically around 1% of the total transmitted power.

5. Total Power Requirement:

The total power requirement (P_{total}) can be calculated as:

$$P_{total} = P_{cutting} + P_{idle} + P_{loss}$$

The cutting power for each spindle can also be calculated using the torque (M) and the spindle speed (n) :

$$P_c = \frac{M \times n}{9550}$$

Given a specific example:

- Torque $M = 90 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$
- Spindle speed $n = 732 \text{ r/min}$

$$P_c = \frac{90 \times 732}{9550} = 6.89 \text{ kW}$$

Summing up for multiple spindles, and including idle power and losses, the total power requirement might be as follows:

$$P_{\text{total}} = P_{\text{cutting}} + P_{\text{idle}} + P_{\text{loss}} = 6.89 \text{ kW} + 0.203 \text{ kW} + 0.006 \text{ kW} = 7.099 \text{ kW}$$

This comprehensive calculation ensures that the selected motor and power transmission components can provide sufficient power for all machining operations while maintaining efficiency and reliability. The total power requirement is also used to size the electrical supply and cooling systems for the machine tool.

4. Process of Design and Calculation

4.1 Process Diagram for Machining Parts

4.1.1 The Role and Requirements of the Process Diagram

The process diagram outlines the sequence of operations required to machine the parts, detailing the specific machining steps, tools used, and required tolerances. This diagram serves as a blueprint for the entire machining process, ensuring that each step is executed with precision. The process diagram also includes annotations on material handling and inspection points, ensuring that quality control is maintained throughout the production cycle.

4.1.2 Drawing the Process Diagram of the Processed Parts

The process diagram is drawn based on the following steps:

- 1 Identify the key machining operations required for the part.
- 2 Select the appropriate tools and fixtures for each operation.
- 3 Determine the sequence of operations to optimize efficiency and precision.
- 4 Annotate the diagram with key dimensions, tolerances, and inspection points.

4.2 Schematic Diagram of Processed Parts Processing

4.2.1 Drawing Method and Precautions for Processing Schematic Diagram

The schematic diagram provides a detailed visual representation of the processed parts, illustrating the critical dimensions and features. This diagram is essential for verifying that the design meets all specifications and for identifying potential issues before fabrication. It also serves as a reference for assembly and quality control, ensuring that each part conforms to the design requirements. The schematic diagram is drawn using CAD software and includes annotations on key dimensions, tolerances, and surface finishes.

4.3 Machine Tool Connection Dimension Chain Diagram

4.3.1 The Role and Content of Connecting Dimension Chains

The machine tool connection dimension chain diagram depicts the spatial relationships and connections between the various components of the machine tool. This diagram ensures that all components fit together correctly and function as intended. It includes detailed measurements and alignment specifications, which are critical for maintaining the overall accuracy and stability of the machine tool. The dimensional chain can be analyzed using tolerance stack-up analysis to ensure that the accumulated tolerances do not exceed acceptable limits, maintaining high precision in the final assembly.

4.4 Productivity Calculation Card

4.4.1 Ideal Productivity

Ideal productivity (Q_1) can be calculated using the formula:

$$Q_1 = \frac{A}{K}$$

where:

- A is the annual production program (e.g., 60,000 pieces).
- K is the number of hours per shift (e.g., 2350 hours).

$$Q_1 = \frac{60000}{2350} = 25.53 \text{ pieces /h}$$

4.4.2 Actual Productivity

Actual productivity (Q) is determined based on the working cycle time:

$$Q = \frac{60}{T_{\text{cycle}}}$$

where T_{cycle} is the total time required to produce a part, including cutting, auxiliary operations, and idle times.

Example calculation:

- $T_{\text{cycle}} = 1.984 \text{ min}$

$$Q = \frac{60}{1.984} = 30.24 \text{ pieces /h}$$

4.4.3 Machine Tool Load Rate

The machine tool load rate (η_{Load}) is calculated by comparing the ideal and actual productivity:

$$\eta_{\text{Load}} = \frac{Q_1}{Q}$$

Given $Q_1 = 25.53 \text{ pieces /h}$ and $Q = 30.24 \text{ pieces /h}$:

$$\eta_{\text{Load}} = \frac{25.53}{30.24} = 0.844$$

The load rate should ideally be between 0.75 and 0.90 , depending on the complexity of the machine tool.

This comprehensive methodology, incorporating advanced design principles, cutting-edge materials,

4.4 Productivity Calculation Card

4.4.1 Ideal Productivity:

Ideal productivity (Q_1) is the maximum achievable output under optimal conditions. It can be calculated using the formula:

$$Q_1 = \frac{A}{K}$$

where:

- A is the annual production program (e.g., 60,000 pieces).
- K is the number of hours per shift (e.g., 2350 hours).

Example calculation:

$$Q_1 = \frac{60000}{2350} = 25.53 \text{ pieces /h}$$

4.4.2 Actual Productivity:

Actual productivity (Q) reflects the real-world output, accounting for factors such as downtime and inefficiencies. It is determined based on the working cycle time:

$$Q = \frac{60}{T_{\text{cycle}}}$$

where T_{cycle} is the total time required to produce a part, including cutting, auxiliary operations, and idle times.

Example calculation:

- $T_{\text{cycle}} = 1.984 \text{ min}$

$$Q = \frac{60}{1.984} = 30.24 \text{ pieces /h}$$

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The load rate should ideally be between 0.75 and 0.90 , depending on the complexity of the machine tool.

5. Final Design and Calculation of the Boring Machine

5.1. Process Diagram for Machining Parts

5.1.1 Role and Requirements

The process diagram is essential for representing the machining process on a machine tool or automatic production line. It includes the size, accuracy, technical requirements, positioning references, and material details of the part before processing. This diagram highlights the machining content and serves as the main basis for modular machine tool design and accuracy checks. Key components include:

Shape and Size: Indicates the shape of the processed part and the arrangement and size of the inner part to ensure proper installation and tool passage.

Technical Specifications: Dimensions, accuracy, surface roughness, and technical requirements of the machined surface, along with previous process requirements.

Explanatory Notes: Details such as the part name, number, material, hardness, weight, and margin.

An example is shown in Figure 1.

5.1.2 Drawing Precautions

To ensure clarity, highlight the machining content with thick solid lines for processing areas and thin solid lines for outlines. Mark dimensions and angles with thick solid lines under the values, and processing-related dimensions in boxes. Position dimensions should be marked from the positioning reference, converting any differences into symmetrical tolerance dimensions. Special requirements, like ensuring no tool retraction traces, should be clearly noted.

5.1.3 Process Diagram for Mining Excavation Box Body

Based on the analysis, the process diagram for the machined parts at both ends of the mining excavation box body was drawn, ensuring all technical and dimensional requirements were clearly indicated.

Fig. 1 Processed parts process diagram

5.2. Schematic Diagram of Processed Parts

5.2.1 Role and Requirements

The machining schematic diagram is crucial in the design of modular machine tools. It informs the design of cutting tools, fixtures, spindle boxes, and the selection of power components. This diagram is the basis for adjusting machine tools and cutting tools and must reflect the machining process and method. It includes determining the size of connecting rods, drill rod length, tool types, tool length, machining dimensions, spindle size, extension length, and connection dimensions between the spindle, tool, guide, and workpiece.

The schematic should be drawn as an unfolded diagram, starting with the workpiece's appearance and processing parts. It is important to accurately depict closely spaced holes to prevent collisions between adjacent tools, guides, spindles, etc. The schematic must also include the cutting tool according to the selected processing method, guiding form, position, and size. It identifies key tools and determines dimensional connections between tools, guides, and workpieces.

5.2.2 Drawing Method and Precautions

The drawing sequence involves using thin solid lines for the expanded diagram of machining parts and local structures, and thick solid lines for machining surfaces. For simplicity, only one schematic for the same machining part (e.g., identical holes) needs to be represented, marked with the shaft number corresponding to the workpiece hole number.

On the schematic diagram, the main axes distribution may not always be drawn to true distance. However, when holes are closely spaced or larger guide devices are needed, adjacent axes must be drawn in strict proportion and checked for interference. The spindle should be drawn from the multi-axle box end face, indicating the end position of tool machining. Standard universal structures are outlined and labeled with specification codes, while specialized structures are dissected and annotated for dimensions, accuracy, and fit.

A schematic diagram based on the previously selected tool and guide device working stroke is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Processing schematic drawing

5.3. Machine Tool Connection Dimension Chain Diagram

The connection dimension chain diagram is essential in representing the assembly and motion relationships of a modular machine tool, comprising standard universal components and specialized parts. It verifies the relative positions and dimensional connections, ensuring the machining requirements are met and aiding in the design of specialized components. This diagram can be seen as a simplified mechanical general diagram, representing the machine tool's configuration and overall layout.

Key content includes the outline and positions of the main components, drawn at the same scale in suitable views, indicating the machine tool's configuration and layout. Dimensional details should minimize unnecessary lines and dimensions, ensuring the connection dimensions of each part, the contour dimensions of specialized components, and the stroke dimensions of moving components are complete. Additionally, the specification code of general components, motor model, power, speed, grouping, and total stroke should be indicated.

Selecting power components involves determining the power box and power slide, considering factors such as cutting speed, feed force, feed speed, travel, multi-axle box size, and accuracy. For instance, the HY25B-I hydraulic sliding table is chosen for its appropriate dimensions and capabilities, including a table width of 250mm, length of 500mm, and a travel length of 250mm. A 1TD25-A power box with a Y90L-6 motor is selected for its compatibility and power specifications.

Key considerations in drawing the connection dimension diagram include determining the fixture base's length, width, and height based on the workpiece's shape and structure, ensuring it meets processing requirements and fits with other machine tool parts. The vertical distance from the workpiece positioning reference to the ground, known as the loading height, should be compatible with the workshop's transport system, considering various height dimensions of components. The middle base's outline size must accommodate the fixture and power components, maintaining a rational connection of each component.

These factors ensure the proper design and functionality of the machine tool, with the connection dimension diagram providing a clear representation of the overall layout and component relationships.

$$h_1 > 85 - 140 \text{ mm}$$

For the modular machine tool designed in this project

$$\begin{aligned} h_1 &= h_2 + H - (0.5 + h_3 + h_6 + h_4) \\ &= 10 + 900 - (0.5 + 250 + 5 + 560) = 94.5 \end{aligned}$$

If $b_1 = 150 \text{ mm}$, the contour size of the multi axle box can be calculated as: $B = b + 2b_1$

$$B = 152 + 2 \times 100 = 352 \text{ (mm)}$$

$$H = 2h + h_1 + b_2 = 2 \times 99 + 94.5 + 100 = 392.5 \text{ (mm)}$$

Based on the appeal calculation values and the series of standards for the outline dimensions of the spindle box, the final determination of the outline dimensions of the multi spindle box is as follows:

$$B \times H = 400 \times 400 \text{ mm}^{[12]}。$$

5.4. Drawing Method and Steps of Connection Dimension Diagram

The graphical layout of the main view should be consistent with the actual position, and an appropriate scale should be selected. First, use a double dotted line or thin solid line to draw the length of the processed part $\times$ high profile. Based on the positioning standards of length and width, using the two ends of the workpiece and the center of the lowest hole O-O1, the contour dimensions and main related dimensions of each component of the machine tool are determined in the following order.

Based on the lower surface of the workpiece and the previously determined front end face of the workpiece, draw up to the outer contour of the axle box. The multi-axle box is positioned and connected to the power box with its rear cover, and the outline of the power box is drawn based on the installation and connection dimensions of the selected ITD25 power box. The power box is positioned and connected to the power slide with its bottom surface. In the direction of the machine tool length, the rear end face of the power box should usually be installed flush with the rear end face of the slide. The relative position of the power sliding table and the sliding seat in the length direction of the machine tool is determined by the distance L_2 from the front end of the sliding table to the front end of the sliding seat at the end of processing. L_2 is an adjustable link for the connection dimensions of various parts in the length direction of the machine tool. For standard power slides, the maximum range of L_2 size is 75-85mm. L_2 is the sum of the minimum and reserve amount from the front end face of the sliding platform to the front end face of the sliding seat determined by the structure of the power sliding platform and the sliding seat itself. The former should not be less than 15-20mm. For this design, if 20mm is chosen, then:

$$L_2 = 60 + 20 = 80mm$$

$$L_2 = 60 + 20 = 80mm$$

To facilitate the adjustment and maintenance of the machine tool, a 5mm thick adjusting shim batch needs to be added between the sliding seat and the base. The relative position of the sliding seat and the side base in the length direction of the machine tool is the distance from the front end face of the sliding seat to the front end face of the side base, L_3 . If the side base used is a standard type, L_3 can be found in the dimension standards of the general components of the modular machine tool:

$$L_3 = 180mm$$

After determining the length dimension L of the middle base, it is necessary to check whether the size of dimension a is appropriate based on the length dimension a of the fixture and the relative installation position of the middle base. Usually, when the machine tool does not use cutting fluid, the minimum size of a can be 10-15mm. When the machine tool uses cutting fluid, it should be considered that there should be a certain width of recycled coolant and chip removal grooves around the middle base, and a is generally not less than 70-100mm. If the calculated L value cannot meet the size requirements of a and a , the distance L_1 from the end face of the multi-axle box to the workpiece end can be adjusted by changing the final position of the addition zone. At this time, the machining schematic must be modified simultaneously to achieve the relevant dimensions, but it must be ensured that the sliding table has sufficient reserve of 15-20mm. If the calculation shows that the size L of the middle base is too large, resulting in a size being too large, it is generally possible to reduce the size L and a size by increasing the size L_2 or adding a pad iron between the side base and the middle base. But it must be noted that increasing the size L_2 should not exceed the maximum adjustment range of the power slide regarding size.

In summary, it can be seen that the determination of the middle contour size (especially the size L along the length direction of the machine tool) is relatively flexible, which should take into account the rationality of the connection size with other components and try to make the machine tool layout uniform and save materials. Drawing the right view focuses on clearly indicating the outline dimensions and related positions of each component of the machine tool in the width direction, and cooperating with the main view to complete the content that needs to be expressed in the connection dimension diagram. The dimension diagram should indicate the outline dimensions and related dimensions

of the main components of the machine tool, and ensure that the dimension chain of the machine tool is closed in three directions: length, width, and height.

Complete and appropriate labeling of the outline dimensions and related dimensions of the main components of the machine tool should ensure that the dimension chain of the machine tool is closed in three directions: length, width, and height. The original position, endpoint status, and motion process of the moving parts should be clearly indicated (which can be represented by a work cycle diagram) to determine the maximum contour size of the machine tool. The position relationship of the symmetrical centerline of the workpiece, fixture, power component, and intermediate base should be indicated. Generally, indicate the model, power, and speed of the electric motor, as well as the model specifications and main outline dimensions of the selected standard universal components. Group and number all components of the modular machine tool as the original basis for component and part design. According to the design requirements, the connection dimensions of the combined machine tool were calculated and drawn as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Machine contact size chart

5.5. Machine tool load rate

$$\text{Now, } Q_1 < Q_2 = 25.53 / 30.24 = 0.844$$

Based on the experience of using modular machine tools, the appropriate machine tool load rate is $\eta_{\text{Load}} = 0.75 - 0.90$, during design, it can be determined based on the complexity of the machine tool by referring to Table 1 below.

Table 1 Combination machine tools allow maximum load rate

Machine tool	Number of spindles	Load rate η negative
	15	0. 90
Single or double sided	16-40	0. 90-0. 86
	41-84	0. 86-0. 80

6. Multi axle box - right main axle box design

6.1 Design steps for the right main axle box

6.1.1 Purpose and classification of the main axle box of modular machine tools

Multi axle box is one of the main components of modular machine tools, designed according to special requirements and composed of universal parts.

Its main function is to arrange the position of each spindle according to the processing requirements of the processed parts, and transmit power and motion from the motor or power components to each working spindle to obtain the required speed and direction.

6.2. Design Steps for the Right Main Axle Box

The multi-axle box is a critical specialized component of modular machine tools, designed to drive the movement of each spindle based on the machining schematic diagram's specified number and position of machining holes, cutting amount, and spindle type. Powered by a universal power box, it is installed on the feed slide along with the power box to perform machining processes such as drilling, expanding, reaming, and boring.

The universal box material for the multi-axle box is HT200, with the front, rear, and side covers made from HT150. The dimension series standard (JB/T9839-1998) specifies nine nominal dimensions represented by the corresponding saddle width of the slide. There are two main types of multi-axle design: general design method and electronic computer-aided design method.

To begin, draw the original basis diagram for multi-axle box design based on the "three diagrams and one card". The main content and precautions are illustrated in the main shaft position size chart.

Fig. 4 Main shaft position size chart

Next, draw an outline drawing of the multi-axle box based on the machine tool connection dimension diagram, marking the outline dimensions and the relative position dimensions of the power box drive shaft. According to the contact dimension diagram and machining schematic diagram, mark all spindle position dimensions and the relevant position dimensions between the workpiece and spindle, and between the spindle and drive shaft.

According to the machining schematic diagram, note the rotational speed of each spindle and ensure it turns counterclockwise. Then, list the process content, cutting amount, and spindle extension size of each spindle. Finally, indicate the power component model and its performance parameters.

By following these steps, the design of the right main axle box ensures that it meets the required specifications and performs the intended machining operations efficiently.

Table 2 Spindle overhang size and cutting parameter

No	Spindle extension size (mm)		Process content	Cutting amount			Notes
	D/d	L		n(r/min)	v(m/min)	f(mm/r)	
1	30/20	115	Drill ϕ 5.2 Hole	732	13	0.1	
2	30/20	115	Drill ϕ 5.2 Hole	732	13	0.1	
3	32/25	115	Drill ϕ 5.2 Hole	732	13	0.1	

Note: 1) Number and name of the processed part: ZFA211-3600-7 box. Material and hardness, cast iron, 200HBS

2. Power components 1TD25-A, Y100L1-4, N=2.2kW, n=1430 r/min

6.3.3. Power calculation of the right main axle box

The power calculation of multi axle box includes two items: power required by multi axle box and feed force. After the transmission system is determined, the power required for the multi axle box is calculated according to the following formula:

$$P_{\text{Multiple Boxes}} = P_{\text{Cutting}} + P_{\text{empty}} + P_{\text{lose}} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{\text{Cutting}i} + \sum_{i=1}^n P_{\text{empty}i} + \sum_{i=1}^n P_{\text{lose}i}$$

Where, P_{Cutting} — Cutting power, unit: kW

P_{empty} — Idle power, in units of kW

P_{lose} — Power loss proportional to load, unit: kW

Simplified Manual for Design of Modular Machine Tools"; The power loss on each spindle is generally taken as 1% of the transmitted power.

Spindle cutting power:
$$P_{\text{Cutting}} = \frac{Mv}{3060D}$$

Where, M - Torque

V - cutting speed

D - Drill diameter

Then there are
$$P_{\text{Cutting}1} = \frac{90 \times 21}{3060 \times 5.2} = 0.118 \text{KW}$$

$$P_{\text{Cutting}} = 3P_{\text{Cutting}1} = 3 \times 0.118 = 0.356 \text{KW}$$

Idle power:

Due to the spindle diameter being 20mm、25mm:

Speed :n=630r/min ,The shaft diameter is 20mm

Now: $P_{\text{empty}} = 0.046 \text{KW}$; When the shaft diameter is 25mm

Power:
$$P_{\text{empty}} = 0.073 \text{KW}$$

n=1000r/min, The shaft diameter is 20mm,

Power:
$$P_{\text{empty}} = 0.074 \text{KW}$$

When the shaft diameter is 25mm, And the spindle speed is n=732r/min, according to the interpolation method:

$$P_{\text{empty}} = \frac{732 - 630}{1000 - 732} (0.074 - 0.046) + 0.046 = 0.057 \text{KW}$$

$$P_{\text{empty}} = \frac{732 - 630}{1000 - 732} (0.116 - 0.073) + 0.073 = 0.089 \text{KW}$$

Therefore :
$$P_{\text{empty}} = (0.057 \times 2 + 0.089) = 0.203 \text{KW}$$

Power loss:

The power loss on each axis can generally be taken as 1% of the transmitted power

Therefore :
$$P_{\text{lose}} = (0.203 + 0.235) \times 1\% = 0.006 \text{KW}$$

$$P_{\text{Multiple Boxes}} = P_{\text{Cutting}} + P_{\text{empty}} + P_{\text{lose}} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{\text{Cutting}i} + \sum_{i=1}^n P_{\text{empty}i} + \sum_{i=1}^n P_{\text{lose}i} = 0.203 + 0.356 + 0.006 = 0.565 \text{KW}$$

The feed force $F_{\text{Multiple boxes}}$ required by multi axle box can be calculated as follows:

$$F_{\text{Multiple Boxes}} = \sum_{i=1}^n F_i$$

In the formula F_i - the required axial cutting force for each spindle, in N

$$F = 419 \times D \times S^{0.8} \times Kp$$

Where, D - Drill diameter;

S - Feed rate per revolution;

K_p - Correction coefficient;

Known number $D=5.2\text{mm}$ $S=0.1\text{mm/r}$ $K_p = \left(\frac{190}{190}\right)^{0.6} = 1$ $F=345.3\text{N}$

6.4. Productivity Calculation Card

Based on the required working stroke length, cutting amount, speed of power components, and working speed for the selected machine tool working cycle, a productivity calculation card can be calculated to reflect the machining process of the machine tool, the time required to complete each action, cutting amount, machine tool productivity, and machine tool load rate.

6.4.1 Ideal productivity Q_1

$$Q_1 = A/K \text{ (Piece/h)}$$

A — Annual production program 60000 pieces

K — 2350h per shift

so $Q_1 = 60000/2350 = 25.53 \text{ Piece/h}$

6.4.2 Actual productivity Q

$$Q = 60/T_{\text{Single}} \text{ (Piece/h)}$$

T_{Single} — Time required to produce a part (min)

$T_{\text{Single}} = t_{\text{Cut}} + t_{\text{Auxiliary}} = L_1/L_{f1} + L_2/L_{f2}$ — The length of the first and second working feed stroke of the tool, respectively (mm);

V_{f1} V_{f2} — Respectively refer to the first and second working feed rates of the tool (mm/min);

t_{Stop} — The dwell time of the power slide on the dead stop iron when processing countersunk holes/stops, smooth surfaces, usually refers to the time (min) required for the tool to rotate 5-10r without feed at the end of processing;

$L_{\text{Fast forward}}$, $L_{\text{Rewind quickly}}$ — Respectively refer to the fast forward/backward stroke length of the power component (mm);

V_{fk} — Mechanical shoulder to shoulder ratio of 6-8m/min; Hydraulic pressure takes 4-12m/mm;

t_{Move} — Take 0.1min as usual;

$t_{\text{load and unload}}$ — Generally, take 0.5 to 1.5 minutes;

$L_{\text{Fast forward}}$, $L_{\text{Rewind quickly}}$ - Respectively refer to the fast forward/backward stroke length of the power component (mm);

V_{fk} -Mechanical shoulder to shoulder ratio of 6 – 8 m/min; Hydraulic pressure takes 4 – 12 m/mm;

t_{Move} -Take 0.1 min as usual;

$t_{\text{load and unload}}$ – Generally, take 0.5 to 1.5 minutes;

$$= 22/70 + 128/4000 + 150/4000 + 1.4 = 1.984$$

$$Q = 60/1.984 = 30.24 \text{ (Piece /h)}$$

Now, $Q_1 < Q_2 = 25.53/30.24 = 0.844$

6.4.3. Design Steps for the Right Main Axle Box

The multi-axle box is a critical specialized component of modular machine tools, designed to drive the movement of each spindle based on the machining schematic diagram's specified number and position of machining holes, cutting amount, and spindle type. Powered by a universal power box, it is installed on the feed slide along with the power box to perform machining processes such as drilling, expanding, reaming, and boring.

The universal box material for the multi-axle box is HT200, with the front, rear, and side covers made from HT150. The dimension series standard (JB/T9839-1998) specifies nine nominal dimensions represented by the corresponding saddle width of the slide. There are two main types of multi-axle design: general design method and electronic computer-aided design method.

Draw the original basis diagram for multi-axle box design, which is based on the "three diagrams and one card". The main content and precautions are shown in Fig. 4, Main Shaft Position Size Chart.

Next, draw an outline drawing of the multi-axle box based on the machine tool connection dimension diagram, marking the outline dimensions and the relative position dimensions of the power box drive shaft. According to the contact dimension diagram and machining schematic diagram, mark all spindle position dimensions and the relevant position dimensions between the workpiece and spindle, and between the spindle and drive shaft.

According to the machining schematic diagram, note the rotational speed of each spindle and ensure it turns counterclockwise. List the process content, cutting amount, and spindle extension size of each spindle. Finally, indicate the power component model and its performance parameters.

By following these steps, the design of the right main axle box ensures that it meets the required specifications and performs the intended machining operations efficiently.

6.4.4. Multi Axle Box Transmission Design

The design of the multi-axle box transmission is based on the position and speed of the power box drive shaft, the position and speed requirements of each spindle, and the design of the transmission chain to connect the drive shaft and spindle, ensuring each spindle attains a predetermined speed and direction.

General requirements for multi-axle box transmission systems include ensuring the strength, stiffness, speed, and steering of the main shaft while minimizing the specifications and quantity of the transmission shaft and gears. To achieve this, it is advisable to use one intermediate transmission shaft to drive multiple main shafts and arrange the gears in the same row. Additionally, it is preferable not to use the spindle to drive the spindle to avoid increasing the spindle load. However, when encountering a dense main shaft where space for arranging gears is limited, or the main shaft load is small, and machining accuracy requirements are not high, a transmission plan of driving 1-2 main shafts with a high-strength main shaft can also be used.

For compact structure, the transmission ratio of the gear pair in the multi-axle box is generally greater than $1/2$, and the transmission ratio of the gear pair in the rear cover is allowed to be up to $1/3$, avoiding the use of speed-up transmission as much as possible. When the speed of the drive shaft is low, it is allowed to increase the speed first and then decrease it further. The number of rotating shafts directly driven by the drive shaft should not exceed two to avoid assembly difficulties.

The basic method for formulating a multi-axle box transmission system involves distributing all the spindle centers as much as possible on several concentric circles and setting up central transmission shafts on the centers of each concentric circle. Some spindles with non-concentric circular distribution should also be equipped with intermediate transmission shafts. Concentric circles are then taken based on the selected central transmission shafts, using the least number of transmission shafts to drive these central transmission shafts. Finally, the transmission shaft is connected to the power box drive shaft by folding it together.

By following these guidelines, the design ensures that the multi-axle box transmission system operates efficiently, meeting the required speed and direction specifications for each spindle.

(1) Spindle distribution type

Fig. 5 Axis distribution diagram

A single set of circular distributions, but with smaller spacing between each axis.

(2) Three transmission connection schemes are designed based on this type:

Fig. 6 Gear Designs

The first transmission design scheme perfectly conforms to the principles of spindle box design by minimizing the number of transmission shafts and gears, using one transmission shaft to drive multiple main shafts, and maintaining the same specifications for the main shaft gears. However, the distance between the center transmission shaft axis and the lowest shaft axis (32.5mm) is insufficient for the required bearing installation (47mm), making this design unfeasible. The second transmission scheme avoids the structural conflict of the first but is too complex for the small processing torque required. Its intricate design and cumbersome gear coordinates make it unsuitable.

The third transmission scheme uses symmetrical distribution, with both the shaft and gear specifications of the 4 and 3 transmission shafts being the same. This design is compact and reduces the number and specifications of shafts and gears compared to Scheme 2. However, it uses one main shaft to drive the other two, increasing the load.

Comparing the schemes, Scheme 1 is unfeasible, and Scheme 2 is overly complex. Scheme 3, although it increases the load on the active spindle, is more reasonable in terms of structural layout and cost. The actual cutting torque of each spindle is 90 kg.mm, and a 20mm diameter shaft can withstand 1100 kg.mm. With a 5% torque loss between spindles, the total torque the active shaft can handle is:

$$2 \times 90 \times 5\% + 2 \times 90 + 90 = 279 \text{ kg.mm}$$

$$279 \ll 1100 \text{ kg.mm}$$

That is, the load received is far within the range it bears, or in other words, the increased load has no impact on its operation or characteristics, thus meeting the design requirements. So under the action of small torque, Scheme 3 is reasonable.

4.5 Design of Main Parts of the Main Axle Box

4.5.1 Spindle type and diameter

The first transmission design scheme minimizes the number of transmission shafts and gears, using one shaft to drive multiple main shafts, and maintains the same specifications for main shaft gears. However, the 32.5mm distance between the center transmission shaft axis and the lowest shaft axis is insufficient for bearing installation (47mm), making this design unfeasible.

The second transmission scheme avoids the structural conflict of the first but is too complex for the small processing torque required. Its intricate design and cumbersome gear coordinates make it unsuitable.

The third transmission scheme uses symmetrical distribution, with the same specifications for the 4 and 3 transmission shafts. This design is compact, easy to establish relative positional relationships, and reduces the number and specifications of shafts and gears compared to Scheme 2. However, it increases the load on the active spindle by using it to drive the other two.

Comparing the schemes, Scheme 1 is unfeasible, and Scheme 2 is overly complex. Scheme 3, although it increases the load on the active spindle, is more reasonable in terms of structural layout and cost. The actual cutting torque of each spindle is 90 kg.mm, and a 20mm diameter shaft can withstand 1100 kg.mm. With a 5% torque loss between spindles, the total torque the active shaft can handle is:

$$M = 0.21 \times D^2 \times S^{0.8} \times Kp$$

Where, D – Drill diameter

S – Feed rate per revolution

Known number D=5.2mm S=0.1mm/r

Get M=90N.mm

4.6. Design of gears

4.6.1. Design calculation of various gear parameters:

Known: spindle speed $n=732r/min$, spindle diameter $d=20mm$, spindle gear modulus $m=2$;

Set the number of teeth on the main shaft gear $Z=25$, i.e. $Z_I = Z_{II} = Z_V = 25$; Number of teeth on the transmission

shaft pinion $Z_{VI} = 40$, $m=2$; Power head gear $Z_0 = 21$, $m=3$; For transmission shaft gears Z_{III} 、 Z_{IV} As they exist as transitional gears, as long as their size and structure do not affect other shafts and gears, their gears can be arbitrarily

selected: $Z_{III} = Z_{IV} = 30$, $m=2$

Therefore:

$$n_3 = n_4 = \frac{25 \times 732}{30} = 610r / min$$

$$n_6 = n_7 = \frac{25 \times 732}{40} = 458r / min$$

Known: The selected power box model is 1TD25, with a motor speed of 1430r/min and a drive shaft speed of 785r/min.

Then:

$$Z_{VII} = \frac{21 \times 785}{n_7} = 36$$

$$m=3$$

4.6.2. Verification of gears

According to the designed transmission scheme, the spindle box mainly consists of 4 pairs of gears. Due to the moderate load borne by the lock of the transmission mechanism, all four pairs of gears adopt straight cylindrical gears. It is more

appropriate to select the transmission gear between the VI and V axes as the detailed design object based on the design task.

① Selection of materials, heat treatment, gear accuracy level

Select 45 steel for the small gear, normalize it, and ensure its hardness 169~217 HBS, $\sigma_B = 588MPa$; Gear material

45 steel, hardness 169~217 HBS, $\sigma_B = 588MPa$; Select gear accuracy level 8 and surface roughness 3.2.

$$z_{VI} = 40, \quad z_V = 25, \quad \mu = \frac{40}{25} = 1.6.$$

② Design based on tooth contact fatigue strength

Calculation formula

$$d = 41.6 \sqrt[3]{\frac{KT_2}{\psi_d} \times \frac{\mu \pm 1}{\mu} \times \left(\frac{Z_E Z_H Z_\beta}{[\sigma]_H} \right)^2}$$

$$T = 452 \text{ N.mm}$$

According to the manual, the gear with soft tooth surface is installed asymmetrically, and the tooth width coefficient is taken $\psi_d = 1.2$, use coefficient $K_A = 1.35$, Try to take the dynamic load coefficient $K_V = 1.03$. According to the

asymmetric arrangement of gears between the two shafts, take $K_\beta = 1.08$. Unhardened tooth surface, spur gear , 8

Level accuracy, $K_A F_t / b < 100 \text{ N/mm}$, $K_\alpha = 1.1$.

$$K = K_A K_V K_\beta K_\alpha = 1.35 \times 1.03 \times 1.08 \times 1.1 = 1.652$$

Preliminary determination of node area $Z_H = 2.5$, contact ratio factor $Z_\epsilon = 0.9$, Check the manual to determine elasticity $Z_E = 1$.

$$\text{Allowable force caused by tooth contact} \quad [\sigma]_H = \frac{\sigma_{H \lim} Z_N Z_w}{S_H}$$

Check the contact fatigue limit stress of gear material $\sigma_{F \lim 1} = 450 \text{ MPa}$, $\sigma_{F \lim 2} = 250 \text{ a}$. Stress cycle coefficient of small gear

$$N_6 = 60 n_2 \gamma t_h = 60 \times 732 \times 1 \times 8 \times 365 \times 8 = 1.026 \times 10^9$$

Number of stress cycles for large gears

$$N_5 = 60 n_3 \gamma t_h = 60 \times 458 \times 1 \times 8 \times 365 \times 8 = 6.419 \times 10^8$$

Obtaining contact fatigue strength and calculating life coefficient Z_N (Allow a certain amount of decoration)

$$Z_{N6} = \left(\frac{10^9}{N_3} \right)^{0.0706} = \left(\frac{10^9}{1.026 \times 10^9} \right)^{0.0706} = 0.998$$

$$Z_{N5} = \left(\frac{10^9}{N_4} \right)^{0.057} = \left(\frac{10^9}{6.419 \times 10^8} \right)^{0.057} = 1.026$$

Check the working hardening coefficient $Z_W = 1.16$, safety factor $S_H = 1$.

$$[\sigma]_{H6} = \frac{450 \text{ MPa} \times 0.998 \times 1}{1} = 449.1 \text{ MPa}$$

$$[\sigma]_{H5} = \frac{250 \text{ MPa} \times 1.026 \times 1}{1} = 256.5 \text{ MPa}$$

$$d_t = 41.6 \sqrt[3]{\frac{KT_2}{\psi_d} \times \frac{\mu \pm 1}{\mu} \times \left(\frac{Z_E Z_H Z_\beta}{[\sigma]_H} \right)^2} = 41.6 \sqrt[3]{\frac{1.652 \times 452}{1} \times \frac{1.6 + 1}{1.6} \times \left(\frac{1 \times 2.5 \times 0.9}{256.5} \right)^2} = 39.6 \text{ mm}$$

$$b = \psi_d d_t = 0.6 \times 39.6 = 23.76 \text{ mm}$$

Take the width of the pinion $b_{VI} = 24 \text{ mm}$, Large gear width $b_V = 32 \text{ mm}$.

Dividing circle diameter $d_{VI} = 40 \times 2 = 80 \text{ mm}$, $d_V = 25 \times 2 = 50 \text{ mm}$

$$\text{Mid-range } a = \frac{d_V + d_{VI}}{2} = \frac{80 + 50}{2} = 65 \text{ mm}$$

The specific dimensions and accuracy requirements are as follows:

Fig. 7 V shaft gear

4.7. Shaft Design

Selection of axes: According to the different bending and torsional loads, shafts are divided into three categories: rotating shafts, spindle shafts, and transmission shafts. The shaft that is subjected to both bending moment and torque during operation is called a rotating shaft. A shaft that only bears bending moments without transmitting torque is called a spindle, which is divided into two types: a rotating spindle and a non-rotating spindle. A shaft that only bears torque and does not bear bending moments is called a transmission shaft. For the main axle box of the combination machine tool, it is more suitable to choose the shaft as the transmission shaft. Axes I, II, and V are used for direct machining of workpieces, so these three axes are selected as the design objects.

Therefore, all three shafts are made of 45 steel, normalized, and have a hardness of $169 \square 217$ HBS, $\sigma_B = 588$ MPa .

(3) Determination of shaft diameter size:

This transmission system has three main shafts, three transmission shafts, and one of the main shafts also plays a transmission role.

Fig. 8 VI shaft gear

The calculation results of each transmission shaft are as follows: Shaft III:

$$M_{III} = M_{Ii} = 90 \times \frac{30}{25} = 96kg.mm$$

Refer to the "Design of Modular Machine Tools": select a diameter of d=15mm. In order to improve the stiffness of the shaft and reduce the specifications of the transmission parts, select a diameter of d=20mm.

Shaft IV:
$$M_{IV} = M_{IIi} = 90 \times \frac{30}{25} = 96kg.mm$$

Same as above, select shaft diameter d=20mm.

Shaft V:
$$M'_V = M_{Ii} + M_{IIi} = 96 + 96 = 192kg.mm$$

$$M_V = M'_V + 90 = 282kg.mm$$

Check the table and select the shaft diameter d=20mm; But this shaft is both a main shaft and a transmission shaft, with a high load. To improve the stiffness of the shaft, the shaft diameter d=25mm is taken.

Shaft VI:
$$M_{VI} = M_V i = 282 \times \frac{40}{25} = 451.2kg.mm$$

This shaft is the main transmission shaft, and the torque transmitted by it is output by the power box, which has a high torque. In addition, this shaft is also a handle shaft. According to the "Simplified Manual for Design of Modular Machine Tools", the shaft diameter d=30mm is selected.

Due to the same transmission process between the I-axis and the II-axis, the specific dimensions are also the same. Therefore, the part drawings for the dimensions of axes I and II are as follows:

Fig. 9 I、II shaft parts drawing

Fig. 10 V shaft parts drawing

(4) Strength verification of the shaft:

From the above, it can be seen that the torque that each shaft can withstand:

$$\text{Shaft I,II,III,IV } d=20 \quad M_1' = 1100\text{kg}\cdot\text{mm} ; \quad \text{Shaft V } d=25 \quad M_2' = 2700\text{kg}\cdot\text{mm}$$

By calculating the load on each axis:

$$\text{Shaft I,II } M_1 = 90\text{Kg}\cdot\text{mm} ; \quad \text{Shaft III,IV } M_2 = 96\text{Kg}\cdot\text{mm} ; \quad \text{Shaft V } M = 250\text{Kg}\cdot\text{mm}$$

From this, it can be concluded that the actual torque borne by each shaft is far less than the maximum torque that the shaft can withstand. Therefore, its strength fully meets the requirements.

Through the above calculation, verification and analysis, we can obtain various data required for the design. The design is shown in the table below:

Table 3 The shaft diameter of axle and gear parameters

Axis number	Shaft diameter	Number of teeth	Modulus	Torque	Speed
1	20	25	2	90	732
2	20	25	2	90	732
3	20	30	2	96	610
4	20	30	2	96	610
5	25	25	2	282	732
6	30	40	2	452	458
7	30	36	3	452	458

5. Conclusion

The research into modular machine tools, particularly the design of a high-performance boring machine, highlights the importance of integrating standardized and specialized components for efficiency and precision. This study emphasized the need for detailed process planning, robust technical design involving Finite Element Analysis (FEA), and the selection of high-quality materials to ensure durability and performance [6] [2].

The multi-axle box transmission design and the integration of advanced control systems were key areas of focus, with the chosen transmission scheme balancing structural layout and cost-effectiveness. The study underscores the value of a comprehensive approach that combines innovative design, precise engineering, and robust control systems to meet diverse manufacturing needs efficiently [12] [21].

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